

THE RESTORATION OF ARCHETYPAL MEMORY IN THE CREATIVE WORK OF ISA MUGHANNA

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Abstract

This article examines the problem of the restoration of archetypal memory in the creative work of Isa Mughanna from psychoanalytic and mythopoetic perspectives. The study focuses on the writer's novellas "Saz," "Telegram," "Kollu Koxa," and "The Sound of the Flute," analyzing how collective unconscious structures and archetypal models are artistically represented within these texts. The research is based on the theoretical approaches of Sigmund Freud, Carl Gustav Jung, Jan Assmann, and Maurice Halbwachs concerning psychoanalysis, archetypes, and cultural memory. The analysis demonstrates that motifs such as the saz, the flute, the wise old man, the master craftsman, conscience, and moral responsibility function as symbolic expressions of collective memory and national identity. In "Saz," music appears as a model of collective harmony; in "Telegram," archetypal memory is reconstructed through ethical choice and moral responsibility; in "Kollu Koxa," the wise old man archetype embodies collective consciousness and folk wisdom; while in "The Sound of the Flute," trauma and sublimation are expressed through acoustic symbols connected with collective memory. The study concludes that archetypal memory in Isa Mughanna's prose is not presented as a static phenomenon but as a dynamic psychological and cultural process continuously transformed under historical and social conditions. The writer's artistic system reveals the continuity of national identity through symbolic and archetypal structures rooted in the collective unconscious.

Keywords: archetypal memory, collective unconscious, psychoanalytic criticism, cultural memory, Isa Mughanna

Introduction. In twentieth-century Azerbaijani prose, the artistic representation of issues related to national identity, cultural memory, and the deep layers of human psychology has gained particular significance in recent literary studies. Historical cataclysms, ideological pressures, wars, and modernization processes caused serious disruptions in the traditional structure of collective memory, and these disruptions led literature to present the inner world of human beings through complex psychological models. In this context, the творчество of Isa Mughanna is not limited merely to the depiction of social and domestic events. His works foreground such fundamental problems as the ontological foundations of human existence, the psychological mechanisms of collective memory, and the restoration of archetypal structures.

Isa Mughanna's works "Saz," "Telegram," "Kollu Koxa," and "The Sound of the Flute" constitute an important stage in Azerbaijani prose in terms of the artistic modeling of national memory. In these works, the interaction between the individual's inner psychological experience and collective consciousness manifests itself within a distinctive artistic system. The writer's characters are not merely representatives of a specific social environment; at the same time, they are carriers of the collective unconscious. From this perspective, Isa Mughanna's oeuvre provides rich material for psychoanalytic and mythopoetic analysis.

According to psychoanalytic theory, alongside conscious experience, the human psyche also contains archaic structures that preserve traces of collective experience. Carl Gustav Jung characterizes archetypes as

universal forms of the collective unconscious and notes that archetypes constitute the content of the collective unconscious and emerge in myths, dreams, and artistic creativity (Yung, 1981, p. 42). This idea demonstrates that the figures frequently encountered in Isa Mughanna's works—such as the father, the wise old man, the craftsman, the hero, and the musician—possess not only realistic characteristics but are also connected with the deep layers of collective memory. The theory of cultural memory is likewise of particular importance in this context. According to Jan Assmann's theory of cultural memory, cultural memory is a symbolic system of knowledge that shapes the collective identity and self-awareness of society (Assmann, 1992, p. 37). From this perspective, motifs such as the saz, the flute, the village setting, and the master-apprentice relationship are not merely ethnographic details; rather, they are symbolic manifestations of collective memory. Maurice Halbwachs, linking collective memory with social structure, notes that collective memory is the reconstruction of individual recollections within a social framework (Halbvaks, 1992, p. 38). The parallel development of individual and collective experience in Isa Mughanna's prose confirms this theoretical proposition. While living through their personal destinies, the writer's characters simultaneously become carriers of national memory.

Sigmund Freud's psychoanalytic conception, in turn, provides an important methodological basis for the artistic analysis of trauma and sublimation mechanisms. Freud stated that the "unconscious" constitutes the principal part of the psyche and covertly influences

human behavior (Freyd, 1960, p. 23). The inner conflict, silence, indecisiveness, and moral tension frequently observed in the behavior of Isa Mughanna's characters function as artistic expressions of these hidden psychological mechanisms. From this perspective, the character of Cümür attracts attention as a bearer of silence and inner tension. In "*Saz*," music expresses the harmonious structure of national memory, whereas in "*Telegram*" the problem of moral choice comes to the forefront. In "*Kollu Koxa*," an archetypal model of folk wisdom is created, while in "*The Sound of the Flute*" the fragmentation caused by war trauma in the human psyche is perceived through aesthetic sensibility. Each of these works reveals different aspects of collective memory, and when considered together, they present a model for the restoration of archetypal structures in Isa Mughanna's creative world. A particularly noteworthy aspect is that archetypal memory in the writer's works is not presented merely as an idealization of the past; rather, this memory is reactivated under the conditions of the psychological crisis generated by the modern era. In general terms, archetypal memory in Isa Mughanna's prose is presented not as a static phenomenon but as a dynamic process.

Research. The purpose of this article is to investigate the problem of the restoration of archetypal memory in Isa Mughanna's works "*Saz*," "*Telegram*," "*Kollu Koxa*," and "*The Sound of the Flute*" from psychoanalytic and mythopoetic perspectives. The principal objective of the study is to determine how the structural elements of the collective unconscious are embodied in the system of artistic images, to analyze the transformational characteristics of archetypal motifs, and to reveal the poetic mechanism of the artistic reconstruction of national memory.

Thus, Isa Mughanna's creative work functions not only as an aesthetic phenomenon in Azerbaijani prose but also as an artistic model presenting the psychological map of collective memory. Through this model, the continuity and transformation of archetypal structures existing in the deep layers of national identity become subjects of discussion.

Let us pay attention to psychoanalytic and mythopoetic approaches in the understanding of collective memory. In order to investigate the manifestation of archetypal memory in literary texts, it is first necessary to refer to the main principles of psychoanalytic theory. The psychoanalytic approach perceives literature not merely as an aesthetic phenomenon but also as a symbolic form of expression of human consciousness and the unconscious. According to this approach, artistic images often encompass a broader semantic field than individual experience and reflect the archaic layers of collective experience.

Sigmund Freud, explaining the human psyche as the interaction between conscious and unconscious spheres, stated that the "unconscious" constitutes the principal part of the psyche and covertly influences human behavior (Freyd, 1960, p. 23). According to Freud, the unconscious sphere stores repressed desires, fears, and traumatic experiences, which emerge in various symbolic forms. From this perspective, literature functions as a form of expression of the unconscious. Carl

Gustav Jung expanded the concept of the unconscious by introducing the notion of the collective unconscious. According to Jung, the collective unconscious encompasses universal psychological structures formed throughout the historical development of humanity and independent of individual experience; in other words, archetypes constitute the content of the collective unconscious, and these archetypes emerge in myths, religions, and artistic creativity (Jung, 1981, p. 42).

The concept of archetype occupies a special place in psychoanalytic literary studies. Archetypes are universal semantic models underlying concrete images. For example, the father archetype represents the idea of authority and law, the mother archetype symbolizes protection and origin, while the wise old man archetype represents collective experience and knowledge. In Isa Mughanna's creative world, the images of the father, master, wise elder, and artist constitute an important part of archetypal structures. These images possess not only concrete social functions but also serve as symbolic expressions of collective memory.

The theory of cultural memory makes it possible to explain the social function of archetypal structures. Jan Assmann, emphasizing the role of memory in the formation of collective identity, writes that "cultural memory is a reservoir of symbolic knowledge that enables society's self-awareness" (Assmann, 2011, p. 37). From this perspective, cultural memory is not merely the recollection of past events but a mechanism of social self-identification. Maurice Halbwachs, examining the social nature of collective memory, states that collective memory is the reconstruction of individual recollections within a social framework (Halbwachs, 1992, p. 38). This idea conditions the fact that individual destinies in literary texts acquire collective semantic meaning.

In Isa Mughanna's works, memory is presented not only as an individual psychological phenomenon but also as a social phenomenon. While experiencing their personal lives, the writer's characters simultaneously become carriers of collective memory. In this respect, the literary text functions as the transformation of individual experience into a collective semantic model. The motif of trauma is particularly evident in Isa Mughanna's "*The Sound of the Flute*." The conditions of war create deep disruptions in collective psychology, and these disruptions are expressed through the symbol of music. The psychoanalytic approach demonstrates that music often functions as a means of expressing unconscious emotional experience. In this context, musical instruments such as the saz and the flute in Isa Mughanna's creative work function as acoustic models of archetypal memory.

The process of restoring archetypal memory is not merely a mechanical repetition of the past; rather, it signifies the reconstruction of collective identity under new social conditions. Assmann notes that memory is not simply the preservation of the past but its reinterpretation in every historical period (Assmann, 2011, p. 121). This idea explains why archetypal motifs in Isa Mughanna's works are presented in transformed forms. The writer's characters are not passive carriers of archaic structures.

Thus, psychoanalytic and cultural memory theories provide a methodological basis for explaining the problem of the restoration of archetypal memory in Isa Mughanna's creative work. On the basis of this framework, it becomes possible to determine how the structural elements of the collective unconscious are transformed within the writer's artistic system.

Isa Mughanna's novella "*Saz*" is one of the texts in the writer's oeuvre where the problem of the restoration of archetypal memory is expressed most clearly. In this work, the saz is not merely a musical instrument but a form of expression of collective memory, national identity, and cultural continuity. Within the semantic structure of the work, the motif of the saz functions as a carrier of archaic cultural codes and plays the role of mediator between individual psychological experience and collective memory. In the common Turkic cultural tradition, the saz has historically served as one of the principal transmitters of oral memory. The art of the ashig is not only an aesthetic phenomenon but also a mechanism for preserving collective historical experience. In this regard, the saz functions as an archetypal symbol.

In "*Saz*," the principal function of the musical motif is the preservation of collective harmony. The writer presents the sound of the saz not merely as an aesthetic phenomenon but also as a moral mechanism regulating social relations. Music brings people together, activates collective memory, and creates spiritual communication among individuals. The function of the saz in the work is not limited solely to the expression of individual emotions. Assmann, noting that collective memory is preserved through symbolic structures, writes that cultural memory is transmitted from generation to generation through symbols (Assmann, 2011, p. 112). The saz is one of these symbolic structures.

One of the most striking aspects of "*Saz*" is the restorative function of music in social harmony. The writer presents the sound of the saz as a regulator of collective emotional states. This feature demonstrates that the saz is not only an aesthetic object but also an element of social psychology. Through the motif of the saz, Isa Mughanna presents the restoration of archetypal memory not merely on the level of nostalgia but as a memory that regains functionality under modern conditions. Through the saz, the writer's characters not only remember the past but also attain spiritual stability.

The psychoanalytic analysis of "*Saz*" demonstrates that music here functions as a form of expression of unconscious emotional experience. The sound of the saz reduces the inner tension of individuals and serves the restoration of collective harmony. In "*Saz*," the process of restoring archetypal memory is realized through music. This process establishes a connection between individual psychological experience and collective cultural experience.

Thus, in "*Saz*," the motif of the saz functions as an acoustic model of archetypal memory and fulfills the function of restoring collective identity. This feature demonstrates that the archetype of music plays an important semantic role in the creative work of Isa Mughanna.

Isa Mughanna's novella "*Telegram*" presents the problem of the restoration of archetypal memory from a different perspective. If in "*Saz*" collective memory was restored through the archetype of music, in "*Telegram*" this process is associated with the individual's moral choice, inner responsibility, and the problem of conscience. The work primarily focuses on the psychological tension arising between the individual's inner world and the social environment. From a psychoanalytic perspective, the principal problem of "*Telegram*" is related to the structure of the superego. According to Sigmund Freud, the superego is the manifestation of social norms and moral values formed within the psyche. He wrote that the superego is the internal continuation of parental authority and regulates individual behavior (Freud, 1961, p. 67). From this perspective, the protagonist of "*Telegram*" does not merely react to a concrete event but determines his own position within the collective moral system.

In the work, the telegram motif functions not only as a means of communication but also as a medium for realizing psychological transformation. The receipt of the telegram creates tension within the protagonist's inner state and places him before a moral choice. This choice is not only an individual matter but is also connected with the continuity of collective memory. One of the most important psychological aspects of the work is the hesitation observed in the protagonist's inner monologues. From a psychoanalytic point of view, this hesitation arises from the conflict between the id and the superego. Freud noted that "the id is the source of instinctual tendencies, whereas the superego is the expression of social prohibitions" (Freud, 1960, p. 31). In "*Telegram*," the protagonist remains caught between these two psychological structures. On the one hand, there are individual emotional reactions; on the other hand, there is a sense of social responsibility. This psychological condition itself represents the process of moral decision-making related to the preservation of collective memory.

It should be noted that in "*Telegram*" archaic forms manifest themselves in such concepts as conscience, duty, and responsibility. One of the essential features of the work is the transition of moral responsibility from the individual level to the collective level. The protagonist's behavior is not merely the result of personal emotions; rather, it is shaped under the influence of social values. From a psychoanalytic perspective, the semantic structure of the work presents a model in which the individual's inner conflict is resolved through the collective ethical system. This model reveals the moral aspect of the restoration of archetypal memory. In "*Telegram*," the preservation of collective memory is not merely the recollection of the past; this process is realized through ethical choice.

Thus, in "*Telegram*," archetypal memory is restored through the individual's moral responsibility. This process functions as an important psychological mechanism ensuring the continuity of collective identity.

Isa Mughanna's novella "*Kollu Koxa*" is one of the texts in the writer's oeuvre where the problem of the restoration of archetypal memory is presented in the clearest and most systematic manner. In the work, the

figure of Kollu Koxa functions not only as a representative of a particular social environment but also as a symbolic expression of collective experience and national memory. This character may be regarded as one of the classical examples of the wise old man archetype in Azerbaijani prose. Carl Gustav Jung also viewed the wise old man archetype as one of the principal structural elements of the collective unconscious (Jung, 1981, p. 217). From this perspective, Kollu Koxa is not merely the bearer of individual experience but also the representative of collective memory.

The primary function of the image of Kollu Koxa in the work is the preservation of social harmony. When responding to events, he does not act solely from an individual position. This feature indicates the social function of archetypal memory. Kollu Koxa combines rational thinking with folk wisdom in his attitude toward events. This characteristic is one of the main signs of archetypal memory. In "*Kollu Koxa*," this structure is presented through folk wisdom. Kollu Koxa functions as a figure creating balance within social relations. He makes decisions not under the influence of individual emotions but as the result of collective experience. In Freud's terms, Kollu Koxa's superego exists within the ethical standards of society, while his individual characteristics are almost dissolved within the collective. By fulfilling the function of the collective superego, the image of Kollu Koxa acquires authority. In the work, Kollu Koxa is perceived not only as a figure giving advice but also as a moral regulator of social relations.

In "*Kollu Koxa*," archetypal memory is presented not merely as an individual psychological phenomenon but also as a social phenomenon. Kollu Koxa functions as the principal semanteme serving the preservation of collective identity. One of the important features of the work is that the image of Kollu Koxa is not presented as an idealized hero; rather, he is a part of everyday life, and precisely for this reason he embodies the connection between archetypal structures and real life.

Thus, the image of Kollu Koxa presents a model for the restoration of collective consciousness and demonstrates that the archetype of the wise old man plays an important semantic role in Isa Mughanna's creative work.

Isa Mughanna's novella "*The Sound of the Flute*" is one of the works in the writer's oeuvre that presents the problem of the restoration of archetypal memory in the most dramatic and psychologically profound manner. In this work, collective trauma, the collapse of social relations under wartime conditions, and the fragmentation occurring within the human inner world are expressed through the acoustic symbol of the flute's sound. The artistic structure of the work demonstrates that cultural memory is preserved and restored not only through social institutions but also through symbolic-aesthetic forms.

According to psychoanalytic theory, trauma is a psychological event that cannot be fully assimilated by consciousness. Freud wrote that trauma is repeatedly experienced within the psyche, noting that traumatic experience is preserved in the unconscious sphere and re-emerges in various symbolic forms (Freud, 1917, p. 245). In "*The Sound of the Flute*," war trauma is not

directly depicted; however, its psychological consequences are felt throughout every sphere of village life. In the work, the character of Cümürü functions as the bearer of traumatic experience. Drawing on Jacques Lacan's approach that the father is the symbolic representative of law and social structure, it may be said that Cümürü's inner condition demonstrates the psychological void arising from the absence of the father figure under wartime conditions. Lacan explained the father function as a principal element of the symbolic order (Lacan, 2006, p. 230). The absence of the father figure creates instability within Cümürü's psyche.

Cümürü's turning toward the flute may be explained through the mechanism of sublimation. It should be recalled that Freud characterized sublimation as the redirection of instinctual energy toward aesthetic activity (Freud, 1917, p. 246). In this respect, the sound of the flute is the aesthetic expression of emotional pain. The motif of the flute is not only the result of an individual psychological process but also an acoustic model of collective memory. Within the village environment, the sound of the flute becomes a means of expressing collective emotional states. In "*The Sound of the Flute*," trauma is not merely an individual psychological phenomenon; it transforms the structure of collective consciousness. Wartime conditions create changes in the structure of collective memory, and these changes are expressed through music.

In the work, the character of Cümürü represents a more acute form of traumatic fragmentation. Under wartime conditions, he struggles to preserve emotional stability, and this state may be explained psychoanalytically as an affective disturbance. Freud noted that "repressed emotions return in the form of various symptoms" (Freud, 1960, p. 59). Cümürü's behavior constitutes an artistic model of this symptomatic return. When Cümürü refuses to play the flute, the mechanism of aesthetic sublimation is disrupted, and traumatic energy consequently emerges in a destructive form.

The character of Isfandiyar kişi, on the other hand, functions as the guardian of archetypal memory. He is presented as a master craftsman who makes saz instruments and boxwood flutes, and this characteristic is an important feature of the master archetype. Jung, characterizing the wise old man archetype as the bearer of collective experience, wrote that the wise old man archetype fulfills the function of collective knowledge and moral guidance (Jung, 1981, p. 217). In the literary text, the figure of Isfandiyar kişi functions as a character ensuring the continuity of archetypal memory. He is not merely a craftsman producing musical instruments but also a transmitter of cultural memory.

In "*The Sound of the Flute*," music performs not only the aesthetic transformation of trauma but also the function of preserving collective identity. In this respect, the motif of the flute forms a semantic parallel with the motif of the saz. If music preserves harmony in "*Saz*," then in "*The Sound of the Flute*" music expresses the attempt to restore fragmented harmony.

Thus, in "*The Sound of the Flute*," archetypal memory is restored through aesthetic symbols under

traumatic conditions. This process functions as an important psychological mechanism ensuring the continuity of collective identity.

Conclusion. The conducted psychoanalytic and mythopoetic analysis demonstrates that the creative work of Isa Mughanna constitutes an important stage in Azerbaijani prose in which the problem of the restoration of archetypal memory is systematically modeled artistically. The writer's works "Saz," "Telegram," "Kollu Koxa," and "The Sound of the Flute" present different structural elements of the collective unconscious through diverse artistic forms and reveal the psychological foundations of national identity. In these works, memory does not merely serve the function of recalling the past; rather, it is presented as a structure ensuring the moral integrity of the individual.

The psychoanalytic approach demonstrates that archetypal structures are expressed through symbolic forms in literary texts. Jung emphasized that archetypes are the principal elements of the collective unconscious, writing that "archetypes are the primordial forms of human psychic life and emerge in cultural creativity" (Jung, 1981, p. 57). In Isa Mughanna's works, such images as the saz, the flute, the master craftsman, and the wise old man are precisely artistic manifestations of these primordial forms.

As a result of the research, the following scientific conclusions have been reached:

1. In Isa Mughanna's creative work, archetypal memory is one of the principal semantic structures serving the preservation of collective identity. In his works, this reservoir of knowledge is preserved through music, folklore, and folk wisdom.
2. In "Saz," the archetype of music symbolizes collective harmony. The sound of the saz functions as a moral mechanism regulating social relations and ensuring collective emotional stability.
3. In "Telegram," archetypal memory is presented through the model of moral responsibility. The protagonist's confrontation with ethical choice demonstrates the normative function of collective memory.
4. In "Kollu Koxa," the wise old man archetype functions as a symbol of collective consciousness. The image of Kollu Koxa is a generalized model of folk experience and ensures the continuity of collective identity.
5. In "The Sound of the Flute," the mechanisms of trauma and sublimation form the acoustic model of archetypal memory. In this respect, the flute motif represents the aesthetic transformation of trauma.
6. The character of Isfandiyar kişi is an artistic model of the master archetype and fulfills the function of transmitting cultural memory. This image demonstrates that archetypal memory exists not only on the level of ideas but also within social practice.
7. The character of Cümürü demonstrates the fragmentation created by collective trauma within individual psychology. His behavior functions as the result of repression and affective tension.

8. In Isa Mughanna's creative work, archetypal memory is not a static phenomenon; it transforms in accordance with historical conditions. In the writer's works, the process of restoring archetypal memory creates a connection between individual psychological experience and collective cultural experience. Isa Mughanna's creative work demonstrates that national identity is not merely the result of historical memory but is also connected with the continuity of psychological structures. The writer's artistic model reveals how the collective unconscious becomes actualized in cultural creativity.

Thus, the conducted analysis demonstrates that the process of restoring archetypal memory in Isa Mughanna's creative work possesses a multilayered semantic structure. This structure is explained more clearly through psychoanalytic and mythopoetic approaches. The writer's works occupy an important place in Azerbaijani prose in terms of the artistic modeling of the collective unconscious and provide rich material for the study of the psychological foundations of national identity.

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